

ADVANTAGES AND VALUE OF ENGLISH IDIOMS WITH TRANSLATION (TARJIMA BILAN INGLIZ TILIDAGI IDIOMALARNING AFZALLIKLARI VA QIYMATI)

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Avazova Munira Sobir qizi

QDU filologiya va tillarni o'qitish (ingliz tili) yo'nalishi 3-bosqich talabasi

Annotatsiya: Tilning lug'at tarkibini tashkil etuvchi birliklardan biri frazeologizmlardir. Frazeologizmlar til birligi sifatida nutqda namoyon bo'ladi. Ular nutqning ta'sirchan va buyoqdor bo'lishini ta'minlaydi. Frazeologik birliklar ma'lum bir tilda so'zlashuvchi xalqning madaniy til boyligini aks ettiradi va ularning dunyoqarashining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini ochib berishga yordam beradi. Har bir tildagi frazeologizmlarni o'rganish muhim hamda qiziqarli hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada frazeologik iboralarni o'rganilish holati bo'yicha ayrim mulohazalar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazeologiya, frazeologik lug'atlar, frazeologizm, ibora, tarjima.

Annotation: one of the units that make up the dictionary composition of the language is phraseologisms. Phraseologisms are manifested in speech as a unit of language. They ensure that the speech is expressive and colloquial. Phraseological units reflect the cultural language wealth of a people speaking a certain language and help to reveal the peculiarities of their worldview. It is important and interesting to learn phraseologisms in each language. In this article, some considerations on the state of the study of phraseological phrases are discussed.

Keywords: phraseology, phraseological dictionaries, phraseology, phrase, translation.

Аннотация: одной из единиц, составляющих словарный состав языка, являются фразеологизмы. Фразеологизмы проявляются в речи как языковые единицы. Они обеспечивают выразительность и выразительность речи. Фразеологизмы отражают культурное языковое богатство народа, говорящего на том или ином языке, и помогают раскрыть особенности их мировоззрения. Изучение фразеологизмов в каждом языке важно и интересно. В данной статье приведены некоторые соображения относительно ситуации изучения фразеологических выражений.

Ключевые слова: фразеология, фразеологические словари, фразеологизм, словосочетание, перевод.

As in any other language, the meaning of English idioms is often incomprehensible at first glance, hidden under the centuries (and sometimes thousands of years) of a network of cultures and language formation. It is necessary to carefully and separately study the meaning of each phrase. It seems a difficult and long process, but it is interesting to constantly plunge into the world of incomprehensible meanings. Especially local sentences are tied to the case, and comparison and comparison begin. String-like vine branches To consider phraseological units as an integral integral part of the language

excellent study of the general and specific laws of phraseology requires withdrawal. Analysis of the semantic stylistic characteristics of phraseological units doing, as everyone knows, is a much more extensive coverage area. By phraseology many linguists make their worthy contributions to the development of scientific research added. Still many believe that phraseology is formed as a separate part of linguistics although there was no time, the history of its origin was the first of the language development stems to stages. From scientific research it is known that phraseological the units appeared together with the language and developed together with the language. However in different periods of society, their role and importance are assessed differently.

Phraseologism, phraseological unit, phraseology — the general name of stable (stable) gardens, consisting of two or more words, spiritually equivalent to a related word combination or sentence, applied in a sense of integrity in a portable and indivisible. F.lar, unlike syntactic structures, in which the form is similar to their own, uses speech as a free choice of speech, not by substitution, but as a material with a meaning and a certain lexical grammatical composition, ready from the beginning, that is, F. from the composition it is impossible to take out, drop a piece: the seeds of Anka, beat the barley raw, count the chuchvara raw, roll out without skin, fly the butterfly, fall into the place of skates, the sheep is open, the ear is heavy and the other F.lar has historical norms of application, methods, their meanings are clarified in a certain conversational process . For English learners, sometimes they find it difficult to translate idioms into exactly their own language. Especially this requires a lot of effort and more research for researchers who are constantly engaged in translation work. This article highlights some of the research work done on idioms in which words of body

members participated, with gone on to help those difficulties. Illuminated and commented bills using examples to add clarifications mentioned. The following idioms always require translation, taking into account the presented situation, and first of all it is necessary to make sure that this combination is an idiom and then go to the analysis. Our article, which is presented, is made in the desire of these problems. *Idioms or phraseologies exist in every language. To learn a foreign language, so as not to get into an uncomfortable situation, it is necessary to learn idioms. In English, there are many complex phrases and turns that the British like to use in everyday life. These idioms affect different spheres of life: food, animals, weather, etc. In this article, you will learn what English idioms are and whether they are worth learning or not. English idioms or phraseologies-these are unstressed speech turns, the unstressed combination of words is usually understood in a figurative sense. The meaning of the whole phrase is not determined by the meaning of the words included in it. Often it is difficult to guess the meaning of the idiom, it is difficult to understand from the words that enter it, if you are unfamiliar with it.*

Let's discuss and see some ideoms and their meanings in uzbek.(time)

- 1.AGAINST TIME-vaqtga qaramay tez bajarmoq
- 2.CALL IT A DAY- ishlashdan to'xtamoq
- 3.DEVIL OF A TIME- yomon vaqt o'tkazmoq
- 4.CLOCK ON- kelgan vaqtini yozmoa
- 5.CLOCK OUT- ketgan vaqtini yozmoq
- 6.HIGH TIME- ayni vaqti
- 7.KILL TIME- vaqtini behuda sarflamoq
- 8.MATTER OF A TIME- vaqt qadri
- 9.MOMENT OF THE TRUTH- daqiqa qadri
- 10.NAME THE DAY- muhim sanani belgilamoq-
- 11.NOT FOR A MINUTE- bir daqiqa ham emas
- 12.NOW OR NEVER- hozir yoki hech qachon
- 13.PRESSED FOR TIME- vawti tig'iz bo'lmoq
- 14.RACE AGAINST TIME- vaqtga qaramay ish qilmoq
- 15.ROUGH TIME- maqbul vaqt
- 16.TIME FLIES- vaqtzni tez o'tisji
- 17.TO THE LAST- oxirigacha
- 18.THIS DAY- shu kunlarfa
- 19.UP TO DATE- eskirgan
- 20.ZERO TIME- boshlanish vaqti
- 21.DONKEYS YEARS- Ko'p yillar

22. IN THE LONG RUN- keyinchalik

22. MONTH OF SUNDAYS- juda uzun vaqt

23. ONCE IN A BLUE MOON- kamdan kam

24. NEVER IN THE MILLION YEARS- Hech qachon sodir bo'lmaydigan

25. NICK OF THE TIME- tig'iz vaqt

For example: to be in the same boat. It literally means: "to be in the same boat", but the meaning of the idiom is different: "to be in the same situation, to experience the same difficulties". To better remember the idiom, you need to understand its meaning, it often seems ridiculous. To understand what this means, it is good to know the history of one or another idiom. Do you remember the story about the cat rain? By the way, in addition to the terrible fairy tales of cesspool, there is another version of its origin (village). In the old days, the houses in the villages were covered with a salmon, which attracted domestic cats and kittens: they preferred to sleep on a soft, fragrant bunny. And those who often come across, but about revenge for our actions "face to face with music" idioms, we also talked about her last time. Strangely enough, it has a "military" origin. On the parade grounds, British soldiers were sued for irregularities and, hearing the verdict, they knocked the drum role not only to the ranks, but also to the orchestra. In short, it was music.

By the way, this English idiom is very suitable for our recent "face-to-face" rotation and is similar in meaning.

We hope that these idioms will help you to colour your speech. Good luck!

There are idioms in the languages of the world. For the Russian language, the word phraseology is more familiar.

Idiom is a combination of several words that have one common meaning. These words lose their individual meaning.

Idioms are called stable, integral combinations, because they are used in an unchanged form. For example, no one talks about sitting on a single boat or being on a single ship. Idiom is used as a ready-made figurative template for some unusual situations.

Perhaps you can guess the meaning of the phrase about the boat, especially when you hear it in context, but there are phrases, it is impossible to guess their meaning.

I want to buy Saturday evening special, but I'm afraid to own it.

What is what -? I want to buy ... Is Saturday night special? Is Saturday night special? maybe I'm afraid to go to trade on Saturday?

"Saturday night special" this is a small gun or revolver. A very approximate phrase can be translated as "special Saturday dinner". It appeared in the 60-ies (now less than threaded), and often inexpensive and inexpensive weapons occurred during a fight with drunkenness in bars, and often in the evening on weekends. The gun was used in many places in hot places, so often during conflicts someone gets a "special meal".

Sometimes the trick is also similar to the threaded - Russian, but has a completely different meaning.

A soft stone does not collect any moss.

This literally means "Moss does not grow on a Rolling Stone". By mistake, you can think that "our water does not flow under the lying stone", but the idiom about Moss has a different meaning: a person who changes his place of residence, profession more often, never sits down. Accordingly, the equivalent: "whoever does not sit in place, he does not do any good." You have learned English grammar, all the rules, hundreds of exceptions. Even an American student can envy your vocabulary. You probably have certificates that you can decorate your wall and speak English well.

What you learn from the textbook and from real life is different. Learning everyday idioms in English will help you to feel comfortable in any situation in life: in a cafe, in a cinema, in a park or in a palm.

To understand idioms, you do not need to translate them verbally. To help you get acquainted with English idioms, we have prepared the best idioms with English translation . In Great Britain, they do not talk about politics, religion, family. Especially with strangers. The only acceptable topic for conversation is weather. Therefore, many English Idioms - on this topic.

It's raining cats and dogs - it's raining. In Russian - it is poured like a bucket.

This English idiom appeared in the 18th century. He is an English writer J. Introduced by Swift. In those days, there was a bad protection of sewer pipes. They even went through the rain. All content, including domestic animals: the bodies of cats and dogs were spilled.

To steal a thunderstorm is to steal someone's idea.

This English idiom came from theatres in the 18th century. There were no sound instruments, and the lead balls were shaken into a bowl to form a thunderstorm. Playwright J. Dennis used metal in his work. The play was rejected, but Dennis ' idea of metal balls was stolen.

Then he shouted the phrase, which became English idiom: "they stole my lightning!"- They stole my lightning. Phrases and idiom are one of the essential part of English grammar

Idioms in English with translation

In America, these English words are one of the most common in everyday speech. You will hear them in the movies and TV shows. Use them and your English will look like native speakers

English has a thousand-year history. During this time, he collected many phrases that people found successful, well-aimed and beautiful. Thus, a separate layer of language appeared - phraseology, a collection of phrases with an independent meaning. In our country, the study of English is widely established, including good knowledge of English, without knowledge of its phraseology is not possible. Knowledge of phraseology significantly facilitates the reading of both artistic and artistic literature. Rational use of phraseological units makes speech idiomatic. The aesthetic aspect of the language with the help of phraseological phrases, which is literally not translated, but perceived in a rethinking way. "With the help of idioms, with the help of different shades of colour, the informative aspect of the language is filled with an emotional-intuitive image of our world, our life" The world of modern English phraseology is huge and diverse, and every aspect of its study, of course, deserves attention. The purpose of this work is to examine the phraseological units of modern English language derived from artistic and literary sources. This aspect of the study of phraseologies is of particular importance, because. Most of the phraseological units were mastered from English and other languages artistic literature, while some phraseological units retained their original foreign language form. Borrowing is one of the main sources of replenishment of the English phraseology. Debts from English literature are especially numerous. It is mastered separately from the literature of Latin, Greek, French, Spanish, Italian and other languages. "The etymological aspect of the study of phraseological units in many ways helps to understand the culture and life of peoples in which he or she has mastered this phraseological phrase" For those who are studying English as a foreign language, it is difficult to master this layer of language, but after mastering phraseological unit.

It is known that phraseological units are a language that makes up the dictionary wealth of each language unit and they will be available in ready-to-speech as a unit of language. They also took into account their semantic characteristics, like other language units in the case such as synonymy, antonymia, homonymy, paronymia and polysemia three to events. Phraseological polysemia means the phraseological unit itself and it is understood that it has more lexical meanings. Free, similar in shape

meanings from the garden and phraseological unit to a point combined, it can not be regarded as polysemy. Because these are all different phenomena: free a link is a unit of speech, a phraseological unit is a unit of language. For example, take the car dry at dodging or grasp straws are used in drawing up a free combination speech, however straws phraseological units at dodging or grasp dry cart are also available in grammar. From the first, the correct meaning, and from the second, the portable meaning (from the "odd to speak to an excess degree about a work or thing that can not be done" or "no something to hope or help in a difficult situation when there is no way out do and seek") is understood. It is not a language unit of meanings, but two each polysemy does not occur because it means different language phenomena. Above is the attitude (equivalent to The Shape of the phraseological unit with a free link accident) referred to as survivability. If the lexical meaning of the phraseological unit is more than one, then in the same lexemes as it is done, the main meaning and harvest are determined by the meaning. For example, to insert a jar phraseological unit "broadcast through the mouthpiece" (this has become an old meaning), means "distribute messages to more than necessary level". Also, English-language to make a getaway phraseological unit "committing a crime and "escape from a boring political system" means. The first-the main meaning, the second - the derivative from which it grew. The development of the lexical meaning is also characteristic of phraseological units it is an event. In the present-day Uzbek and English phraseological units, the lexical meaning is mainly developed as a result of the transfer by metaphor. For example, to cheer up the phraseological unit is due to the fact that in the original something to be consumed more often in the dish "get burned" it means This phraseological unit then goes from food to something else, it was also used to look at people, as a result of such a transfer it not coinciding with the nature of the phraseological unit, "the feeling of dislike awakened" meaning is formed. Or English-language to walk all over somebody phraseological there is a similar look in the unit walk. I'm not about to let them walk all over me. 2) but every day is the same repeating the thing touched her heart. We expected Williams to walk all over her. A phraseological unit as a result of the development of a specific meaning the amount of meaning varies. Second phraseological on the basis of one phraseological meaning the birth of meaning leads to two different phenomena - polysemy or homonymy. Homonymy, born with the development of a phraseological meaning, is very small. An example of

this. English and Uzbek at-polysemia when it turns out, it manifests itself in an interesting and enthusiastic state, so on the basis of it knowing how much power he has, he considers himself important, on this basis the transfer led to the birth of a new phraseological unit: the soul came out I - "exhale for the last time" and the soul came out II - "incredibly hard get angry". The second phraseological unit was originally used in the manner of the soul exodus, therefore, by itself, it was distinguished from the first phraseological unit: the previous one if the phraseological unit is used with the relativist of the III person, then the next phraseological unit relativists are used with all three forms of person-number. Second later in the phraseological unit appeared variants of pronouncing the soul, and in two phraseological the separation into Unity has become even more pronounced. A phraseological unit also refers to contradictory meaningful lexical meanings. For example, the phraseological unit of the origin of the sheath of the heart is a severe excitation means, but such a situation is connected both with anxiety and with joy: 1) I will not be afraid, my son. The heart of a person at that time it goes out of the sheath. 2) as soon as the girl saw her paranoia, the guy's heart could get out of his vagina. This one it can be likened to the phenomenon of enantiosemia. Most phraseological units are monosemantic. For example, go through the Bahri phraseological unit "to give up what it considers useful", something without waiting until the phraseological unit "talked say", or go over somebody's head phraseological unit "for nothing misunderstanding "ni, get down to brass tacks phraseological unit" an important issue it means" to start a discussion". The polysemantic phraseological units are also significant in the Uzbek language and are used in English less than in the language. No more than two polysemantic phraseological units. the transfer led to the birth of a new phraseological unit: the soul came out I "exhale for the last time" and the soul came out II - "incredibly hard get angry". The second phraseological unit was originally used in the manner of the soul exodus, therefore, by itself, it was distinguished from the first phraseological unit: the previous one if the phraseological unit is used with the relativist of the III person, then the next phraseological unit relativists are used with all three forms of person-number. Second later in the phraseological unit appeared variants of pronouncing the soul, and in two phraseological the separation into Unity has become even more pronounced. A phraseological unit also refers to contradictory meaningful lexical meanings In **Conclusion**, Phraseologisms, unlike syntactic structures, in which the form is similar to their own visually, the free choice of words in speech does not arise by the

way of substitution. Study phraseological phrases from different sides and give it a comprehensive approach, opening its features, generalization anew-new phrases serves to enrich our language on account of.

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